

THE NEED TO DEVELOP FOREIGN LANGUAGE COMMUNICATIVE SKILLS

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ABSTRACT

It is vital that, language is the primary factor for communication and humans attempt to learn language in order to be good communicators. All languages such as English also are learned to gain every field of society: education, medicine, economy or policy and requires having a good command in every skill of the language. Especially, productive skills which are speaking and writing have a crucial role in language learning and teaching. This paper focuses on importance of these skills and effective and innovative and effective ways, methods and approaches will be explored.

INTRODUCTION

According to the recent statistics, there are approximately 6500 spoken languages in the world today and nearly 2000 among these languages have fewer than 1000 speakers. English has become a universal and dominant language as well as serves as an official language of 67 sovereign states and 27 non-sovereign entities. Over the decades it has been learned in ESL and EFL classrooms because of different aims such as studying or better job qualifications. Particularly, besides English grammar productive language skills are more taught by teachers. But what productive skills mean? Prior to discuss this term definition and meaning should be clarified¹. The productive skills are speaking and writing. Because learners doing these need to produce language. They are also known as active skills. They can be compared with the receptive skills of listening and reading. Speaking and writing are more visible to the others and they are also more controlled and guided activities where the primary focus of these two skills is laid on accuracy.

MAIN PART

¹ Rao, P. S. (2019). The Significance of Writing Skills in ELL Environment". *Academia: An International Multidisciplinary Journal*. 9(3), 5-17. DOI: 10.5958/2249-7137.2019.00035.1

Due to the fact that ELLs have to perform in real-life situations, speaking is considered as the most difficult skill. In the real conversations, the ELLs are supposed to give a proper response to the speaker or speakers with whom they are speaking. As the listeners have to give an immediate response to the speaker(s), the ELLs must have good command over both vocabulary as well as grammatical structures of the English language. Furthermore, Learners should figure out slangs, idioms, expressions or figurative terms in real conversations. In ESL and EFL classrooms speaking is also reckoned as an interesting activity that is used more frequently and teachers involve pupils in group and pair activities by creating different situations that are more useful to converse with others in their lifetime. In this regard, Rivers (1978) says, "Speaking is used twice as much as reading and writing". It can also be observed that humans speak more than that of we read, write and listen. Hence, it is more appropriate for the teachers of English to concentrate more on speaking skills by adopting various strategies, techniques and approaches in the English classrooms. Followed by his point of view Olshtain and Cohen state (Olshtain & Cohen, 1991, p.154), "if we wish to master another language we need to become more communicatively competent". Their observation proves the idea that language accuracy is necessary but not the most vital feature of speaking activities. Therefore, in the following some effective techniques are introduced in order to enhance speaking skill of learners from beginners to intermediate ones².

Drama

This technique or activity refers to the making of conversation between two or more students of the class. In this activity, students play a role, such as, a doctor and a patient, a lecturer and a student, a passenger and a driver and so on. This technique is quite similar with role a play; but it necessarily takes much longer time (Byrne, 1994, Parkinson & Thomas, 2000 and Thornbury, 2005). In this activity, the students were asked to record their conversation in like a drama. The lecturer provides time for the preparation until all groups were ready to submit. The lecturer provides the comment and feedback after the recording was submitted. This technique is really interesting and useful not only to develop speaking but also serve to encourage students to use the language in real.

Question and answer

Question and answer is also found as a technique in teaching speaking. This is supported by Richards & Lockhart (1991) as follows: questioning is one of the most common techniques used by lecturer. In some classroom over half of class time is taken up with question-and answer exchanges (Borg & Gall, 1984). This technique can be supported with picture descriptions about different topics. "At the restaurant", "My hometown", "My family " and others³.

Storytelling

Third activity is storytelling. Students can briefly summarize a tale or story they heard from somebody beforehand, or they may create their own stories to tell their classmates. Story telling fosters creative thinking. It also helps students express ideas in the format of beginning, development, and ending, including the characters and setting a story has to have. Students also can tell riddles or jokes. For instance, at the very beginning of each class session, the teacher may call a few students to tell short riddles or jokes as an opening. In this way, not only will the teacher address students' speaking ability, but also get the attention of the class. It is apparent that, for ELLs writing skill is quite complicated and at the same time convenience for communicate in written form. Especially adult learners opt for exploiting

² Richards, J. C. and Schmidt, R. (2002). Language Teaching and Applied Linguistics. Edinburgh: Pearson Education Limited.

³ Makhmudov, K., & Djumanova, B. (2020). Practical techniques for cultural - based language teaching in the classroom. *Young Scientist*, 26(316), 301-303

written conversations by the internet, social sites and e-mails. Schmidt (2002) assert, "Writing is viewed as a result of complex processes of planning, drafting, reviewing and revising". This means writing happens through various operations and ultimately it becomes the final draft. Why is writing as important as speaking? First reason is needs of human being. People have not always opportunity to talk orally and they have to write their plans, ideas, emotions or other circumstances by writing. Therefore, writing is the second easy way to contact. Secondly, writing is a clear substantiation to show real literacy of a person. According to statistics, as a whole, the global literacy rate is high. The literacy rate for all males and females that are at least 15 years old is 86.3 %. Developed nations as a whole have a literacy rate of 99.2 %. Results demonstrate only who has writing skill in the world and it is carried out at schools. Schooling aims to grow multilateral perfect generation for the future life. In this time modern educationalists are expected to use innovative pedagogical techniques to improve learners' writing skill. Writing is not simply producing in written form, it symbolizes useful way of communication, creativity and critical thinking. As scientist Rao P. S. (2019) mentioned "The teachers should understand the level of the students and try to adopt relevant teaching strategies of improving their writing skills that are more suitable for them. Because of a lot of researchers' observations so many effective teaching methods are being announced by the internet pages and utilized in education. Some of them will be discussed in the following⁴:

The Writing Race

This is a simple activity that requires very few resources. It is suitable for learners in beginner level. It also makes writing active and exciting for young learners

– and it allows students to write on the board, which every child seems to enjoy! You'll need to have a relatively small class, preferably less than 15 students, and some space for them to make two rows. Whiteboard / blackboard and whiteboard pens, chalk and timer are needed. This activity is perfect for reviewing vocabulary and practising spelling. This is also a great activity for classrooms without many resources.

Instructions:

1. Choose a topic or lexical set for the class to review and tell them what it is.

Split the class into two teams and ask them to make two lines in front of the board. Give the students at the front of the lines a whiteboard pen/piece of chalk each and set a timer for one or two minutes.

By the way of conclusion, it is demonstrated that active skills are really essential for language learners. And the task for teachers is combine speaking and writing in their lessons to ease and accelerate the language learning process. Moreover, colorful methods and techniques ought to be used in the ESL and EFL classrooms that can develop students' capacity of speaking and writing.

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